

APPENDIX I

RESPONDENT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of research

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Cervical Cancer Prevention and Screening among Healthcare Workers in Selected Local Government Areas in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Name and Affiliation of Researchers

This study is being conducted by the research team from the Department of Community Health and Primary Care, College of Medicine of the University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria.

Purpose of Research

To assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of cervical cancer and its screening among healthcare workers in three selected local government areas in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Potential Benefits

The information obtained in this study will help in creating interventions and policies that would prevent cervical cancer and reduce the morbidity and mortality from it through screening by the health care workers at the primary health care level.

Possible risks, discomfort, and inconvenience

There are no associated risks, discomforts, or inconveniences. The respondents are only required to complete the questionnaire. No personal information is required except the minimum required as evidence that the research was carried out.

Confidentiality

Your responses to this survey will be anonymous. All information that will be collected during the interview is regarded as confidential and will not be used for any other purpose apart from that for which it has been collected.

Willingness to participate

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. It is the choice of the participant to decide whether to participate in this study, and their identity will not be revealed. There is no

incentive attached to participation. Participants can choose to withdraw from the research at any time. A copy of this form will be given to them to keep.

Statement of Person Obtaining Informed Consent

I have fully explained the research to the respondents and given sufficient information, which includes the risks and benefits, to make an informed decision.

Date.....

Signature.....

Statement of Person Giving Consent

I have read and understand the description of the research. I understand that my participation is completely voluntary. I know enough about the purpose, methods, risks, and benefits of the research study to decide that I want to partake in it. I understand that I may freely withdraw from this study at any time without any cost. I have received a copy of this consent form to keep for myself.

Date.....

Signature.....

For further enquiries, please contact:

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Health Research Ethics Committee’s Contact

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APPENDIX II
QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

We are a team of researchers from the College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Idi-Araba, Lagos State, Nigeria. We are conducting a study on the **knowledge, attitude, and practice of cervical cancer prevention and screening among primary health care workers selected from Local Government Areas of Lagos State, Nigeria.**

We humbly solicit your assistance in completing this questionnaire as sincere and accurate as possible. All information you provide will be treated as confidential and strictly used for this research only. **Please do not write your name on the questionnaire.**

Your participation in this study is voluntary, as you are free to decline to participate in the study at any point in time.

Thanks, in anticipation of your cooperation.

Informed Consent

I hereby consent to filling the questionnaire,
(Respondent's signature) _____

INSTRUCTION

Please select the appropriate option or fill in the space required.

SECTION A: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC

1. Age in years
2. Sex: (a) Male (b) Female
3. Marital status: (a) Single, never married (b) Cohabiting (c) Married (d) Divorced (e) Widowed (c) Separated
4. Type of marriage: a) Monogamous (b) Polygamous
5. Ethnicity (a) Igbo (b) Yoruba (c) Hausa (d) Others (please specify)

6. Religion: (a) Christianity (b) Islam (c) Traditional (d) Others (please specify)
7. Number of children (Parity): (a) Nulliparity (none) (b) 1-4 (c) 5 and above
8. Occupation (please specify)_____
9. Qualification level (a) Diploma (b) BSc (c) MSc and above
10. Duration of practice (years) (a)Less than 1 (b) 1-4 (c) 5-10 (d) above 10
11. Income (a) 0 - < 50,000 (b) 50,000 - 100,000 (c) >100,000
- 12.

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER

13. Have you heard of cervical cancer? (a)Yes (b) No (c) Don't know
- 14.

HOW DID YOU GET TO KNOW ABOUT CERVICAL CANCER?	YES	NO
Friends/ relatives		
Media (television, radio, magazines)		
Health seminars/ talks		
Religious organization		
Internet		
Community outreach		
Book		
School/Formal lecture		

S/N	QUESTIONS	True	False	Don't know
14	Cervical cancer is the most common cancer in women			
15	Cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of death in women worldwide			
16	Cervical Cancer is preventable			
17	If detected early, cervical cancer is usually curable			
18	Cervical cancer is most common among women in their 20s			
19	Cervical cancer is preceded by a treatable dysplasia			
20	Cervical cancer can usually be found at an early stage because of the obvious symptoms, such as bleeding and pain.			
21	Cervical cancer is fatal if left untreated			
22	It is possible to detect precancerous cervical cells			
23	The progression of pre-cancerous cells to cervical cancer can take 10-20 years.			
24	Cervical cancer is caused by a virus that is spread sexually			
25	There is a vaccine that can prevent cervical cancer			
26	Screening is a preventive method			
27	The purpose of screening is to detect pre-cancerous changes			
28	Screening for cervical cancer should begin when a woman is in her twenties.			
29	The HPV vaccine is dangerous to health			

	WHAT ARE THE RISK FACTORS OF CERVICAL CANCER	TRUE	FALSE	DON'T KNOW
30	HIV infection			
31	Smoking cigarettes			
32	Having multiple sexual partners			
33	HPV infection			
34	Multiple pregnancies			
35	Poor hygiene			
36	Long-term use of oral contraceptive pills.			
37	Use of an intrauterine contraceptive device			
38	Early sexual intercourse			
39	Alcohol use			
40	Use of herbal remedies			
41	Use of tampons			
42	Impaired immunity			
43	High-fat foods			
44	Having a partner with multiple sexual partners			
45	Poor genital hygiene			

Others (please specify) _____

	Signs and symptoms of cervical cancer include	TRUE	FALSE	DON'T KNOW
46	No symptoms			
47	Abdominal pain			
48	Abnormal vaginal bleeding			
49	Post-menopausal vaginal bleeding			
50	Foul-smelling vaginal discharge			
51	Loss of appetite			
52	Itching in the vagina			
53	Irregular vaginal bleeding			
54	Fever			
55	Pelvic pain			
56	Weight loss			
57	Heavy vaginal bleeding			
58	Pain during sexual intercourse			
59	Postcoital bleeding per vagina			

Others (please specify) _____

SECTION C: KNOWLEDGE ON CERVICAL SCREENING

60. Have you heard of cervical cancer screening? (a) Yes (b) No

61. There are procedures used to detect pre-malignant lesions (a) Yes (b) No (c) Don't know

62	Who can undergo cervical cancer screening?	YES	NO
a.	All females irrespective of age and marital status		
b.	Married women only.		
c.	Women younger than 21 years of age.		

d.	Women above 21 years of age or those who have been sexually active for the last 3 years		
e.	Women above 30 years of age		
f.	Only women above 50 years of age		
g.	Don't know		

64	What are the methods of cervical cancer screening that you've heard of?	YES	NO
a.	PAP smear		
b.	Human Papillomavirus DNA testing		
c.	Liquid-based cytology		
d.	Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA)		
e.	Visual inspection with Lugol's solution		
f.	Cervical biopsy		
g.	Colposcopy		
h.	No methods available		
i.	Don't know		

Others please specify _____

65. How often should the pap smear test for cervical cancer be done (a) Every year (b) Once every 2 years (c) Once every 3 years (d) Once every 5 years (d) Only when symptoms are present (e) Don't know
66. How often should Human papilloma virus DNA testing be done (a) every year (b) once in 2 years (c) Once every 3 years (d) Once in 5 years (e) Only when symptoms are present (e) Don't know
67. Is there a cervical cancer screening test in your health facility (a) Yes (b) No (c) Don't know

68	What are the treatment options for women who test positive after the screening test?	YES	NO
a.	Hysterectomy (removal of the cervix and uterus)		
b.	Cryotherapy		
c.	Loop Electrosurgical Excision Procedure (LEEP)		
d.	Cold knife cone biopsy (cervical conization)		
e.	Trachelectomy (removal of the cervix)		
f.	Radiation therapy		
g.	Chemotherapy		
h.	Targeted drug therapy		
i.	Immunotherapy		

69. Have you heard of the screen and treat algorithm for cervical cancer screening? (a)

Yes (b) No

70. Do you use the screen and treat algorithm for cervical cancer screening in your health facility? (a) Yes (b) No

71. Is there human papillomavirus vaccination in your health facility (a) Yes (b) No (c) Don't know

SECTION C: ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER AND ITS SCREENING

Use the following scale to rate your answers: SA- STRONGLY AGREE, A- AGREE, U- UNDECIDED, D- DISAGREE, and SD- STRONGLY DISAGREE

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	U	D	SD
72.	Cervical cancer screening is an essential part of women's health care.					
73.	I am willing to do visual screening on my patients.					

74.	Screening is too difficult					
75.	Screening can help in early detection and better treatment					
76.	A cervical cancer screening program should be started in my community.					
77.	Screening is too expensive					
78.	My patients have more important issues than cervical cancer.					
79.	I need a lot of additional training to successfully perform screenings.					
80.	I am too busy to screen women					

SECTION D: PRACTICE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

81. Have you ever carried out cervical cancer screening on a patient? (a) Yes (b) No

82	IF YES, WHAT TYPE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING DID YOU PERFORM?	YES	NO
a.	PAP smear		
b.	Human Papillomavirus DNA testing		
c.	Liquid-based cytology		
d.	Visual inspection with acetic acid (VIA)		
e.	Cervical biopsy		
f.	Colposcopy		

Others, please specify _____

83. How many times have you performed cervical cancer screening?

84. If no, why? **Multiple options are allowed** (a) Absence of indication [] (b) Lack of necessary equipment or supplies needed [] (c) Lack of necessary laboratory resources to screen [] (d) I do not have the necessary training to screen, (e) Cervical cancer screening is a doctor's procedure []

Other reasons (Please specify) _____

85. Have you encouraged and /or referred some friends, relations/patients to _____ present themselves for the screening exercise (a) Yes (b) No

86. Do you routinely ask patients if they have been screened for cervical cancer? (a) Yes (b) No

87. If yes, what is the age group of patients you ask? _____

88. Have you ever diagnosed pre-cancerous cervical lesions in a patient? (a)Yes (b)No

89. If yes, what did you? _____

90. Have you ever diagnosed a patient with cervical cancer? (a) Yes (b) No

91. If yes, what did you do? _____

92. Where do you refer patients to if there is a need for referral? _____

93. Have you interpreted the result of the pap smear test to patients requiring such services?
(a) Yes (b) No